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Dear Editor,

Please consider the following paper for publication in Desalination journal.

Title:

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Large-scale solar desalination by combination with CSP: techno-economic analysis of different options for the Mediterranean Sea and the Arabian Gulf

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Abstract

The combination of desalination with Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants (CSP+D) is considered as the most realistic opportunity for the development of large-scale desalination with solar energy. The availability of solar power and waste heat in CSP plants offers possibilities for both reverse osmosis (RO) and thermal desalination systems. In the case of RO the combination can be done directly by transporting the electricity. In the case of thermal desalination technologies there are different alternatives for coupling with CSP plants which can offer advantages with respect to the CSP+RO combination such as the reduction of the cooling needs of the power cycle. A techno-economic analysis of different schemes of multi-effect distillation (MED) systems coupled with CSP plants is presented here and compared to the CSP+RO option. The study is done using validated models of MED plants and considering the three conventional cooling methods available in CSP plants: dry cooling, once-through and wet cooling. The analysis is performed using operating conditions of real plants. The comparisons are done for the two main regions where the cogeneration of electricity and fresh water using CSP+D is proposed: the Mediterranean basin and the Arabian Gulf.

Keywords: solar energy; concentrated solar power; thermodynamic simulation; cogeneration; desalination; power plant cooling.

1. Introduction

Drinking water scarcity is an increasing problem in many regions in the world. Generally, the regions with more freshwater deficit are those with high solar radiation, so the use of solar energy for desalination is a chance for sustainability [1]. Research on solar desalination is progressing constantly and the results are increasingly making this option more attractive. For small communities, the combination of photovoltaic (PV) energy and reverse osmosis (RO) desalination has already been developed into concrete applications that are starting to penetrate the market. However, the large upfront investment required for the solar power supply is a barrier when considering solar desalination for medium or large supplies of water. Furthermore, PV is hardly a dispatchable power and this is a problem for the operation of RO, especially at industrial scale. Until large-size PV power plants can guarantee a constant power supply to the desalination system, the most promising alternative is found in the exploitation of the synergies between concentrated solar power (CSP) production and desalination [2, 3]. The larger CSP dispatchability relies on simpler, more cost-effective and sustainable means for storing energy than PV (i.e., molten salts). However, CSP plants need large amounts of water for their own operation, which jeopardizes their potential installation in many locations where water scarcity is already a problem. The integration of water desalination technologies in CSP plants (CSP+D) can improve the sustainability of the solar power concept, for instance by providing the water that the power plant needs for the cooling system. At the same time, the deployment of desalination can take advantage of the availability of solar electricity and waste heat from the CSP plant.

In the case of thermal desalination, one possibility is to reuse the low-grade energy released to the ambient in the CSP plant cooling system, which can contribute to further increasing the sustainability of the CSP+D concept, especially considering that the condensation of the exhaust steam is a critical issue in CSP. Three cooling systems are commonly used in the power cycle: i) dry cooling, that has the disadvantage of its low efficiency in the warm regions in which CSP plants are commonly installed); (ii) once-through cooling, that requires large amounts of water, generally seawater, to be pumped, adding to the environmental problems the necessity of installing the CSP plant close to the sea, where land is more expensive and the direct solar irradiation is normally slightly lower; and (iii) evaporative water cooling, that requires a constant supply of fresh water to an evaporative tower, a limited resource in arid areas where CSP is usually implemented. The opportunity of CSP+D in the case of integrating a thermal desalination unit is that by using the low or medium pressure steam of the power system, its cooling requirements are decreased.

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5 However, the coupling of thermal desalination systems implies the necessity either to increase the
6 temperature level at turbine exhaust steam or to perform an intermediate steam extraction from the power
7 cycle, which leads to a penalty in the power production.

8 An alternative scenario is to feed the electricity produced by the CSP plant into a RO plant, with the
9 further advantage that in this case the power and the desalination plants can be installed in different locations
10 provided they are communicated by the electric grid.

11 The combination of water desalination and concentrated solar power production is still in the R&D phase
12 and some aspects are yet to be properly determined in order to achieve an effective integration of both
13 technologies. The main issue is the choice of the most adequate desalination technology. Several studies
14 related to the combination of RO and thermal desalination units with CSP plants have been published in the
15 literature covering different areas of the world [4-11]. Most of them consider a low-temperature Multi-Effect
16 distillation (LT-MED) plant for the thermal desalination, since this process is more efficient
17 thermodynamically than Multi-Stage Flash (MSF) [12]. Also, in most cases the thermal desalination system
18 is considered to fully replace the condenser of the power plant. This can be a large risk towards the
19 implementation of a CSP+D demonstration plant, since the power production is therefore entirely dependent
20 on the desalination system. Moreover, when it is used directly as the heat source of the desalination plant the
21 exhaust steam is not expanded to a pressure as low as in the case of standalone CSP plants, so the efficiency
22 of the power cycle decreases. The authors of this paper have already considered alternative configurations
23 which do not eliminate the condenser of the power cycle [9-11]. These approaches, besides allowing the use
24 of the power cycle condenser in case of failure or maintenance in the desalination plant, provide further
25 advantages such as allowing the exhaust steam to expand to a lower pressure and decoupling the fresh water
26 production from the electricity production. However, the study of these alternatives for different cooling
27 systems in the CSP plant and for different locations has not been done yet. This paper addresses that matter
28 by presenting a detailed techno-economic analysis of the typical coupling of a LT-MED to a CSP, together
29 with two other configurations based on the use of a conventional Thermal Vapor Compression Multi-Effect
30 Distillation (TVC-MED) plant and a LT-MED powered by a thermo-compressor. The comparison of these
31 configurations with respect to the combination between a CSP and RO is carried out, considering the three
32 cooling methods for the CSP plant. The analysis has been performed for two representative locations for the
33 Mediterranean basin and the Arabian Gulf.

34 2. CSP+D configurations proposed

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36 CSP plants are based on the concentration of the direct (non-diffuse) component of the solar radiation to
37 produce high temperature steam from which electricity is generated as in other thermal power systems. In
38 this study, the CSP plant is based on the most conventional configuration: a parabolic-trough (PT) collector
39 solar field orientated North-South; a thermal storage consisting in two tanks filled with molten salts; and the
40 power block. The collectors are Eurotrough type with the following dimensions and characteristics: aperture
41 area of 817.5 m², 150 m total length, and a peak optical efficiency of 80 %. The heat transfer fluid that
42 circulates through the absorber tubes of the collectors is thermal oil, namely Monsanto VP-1, whose
43 maximum operational temperature is 400 °C. For the power block, a reheat Rankine power cycle is used. The
44 cycle includes a reheat process after the high pressure turbine (HPT) body and five steam extractions from
45 the low pressure turbine (LPT) body. Each flow of steam extracted feeds a heater in order to preheat the feed-
46 water flowing to the steam generation system of the power cycle. The incorporation of the heaters in CSP
47 plants is a usual practice to improve the cycle efficiency compensating the lower operational temperature
48 with respect to conventional fossil power plants.

49 The four different CSP+D configurations considered are:

- 50 • Configuration #1: LT-MED unit integrated into a CSP plant.
- 51 • Configuration #2: LT-MED+TVC unit integrated into a CSP plant.
- 52 • Configuration #3: TVC-MED unit integrated into a CSP plant.
- 53 • Configuration #4: RO unit connected to a CSP plant.

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56 In Configuration #1 (see Fig. 1), the steam leaving the LPT is fully condensed in the first effect of the LT-
57 MED unit, which produces fresh water through the evaporation-condensation processes that takes place in
58 each effect of the desalination plant. In this case, the steam is not left to expand to the pressure of a
59 standalone CSP plant, so only four extractions can be taken from the LPT instead of the typical five (as in
60 Configurations #2 to #4).
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5 In Configuration #2 (see Fig. 2), part of the exhaust steam is used as the entrained vapor in a steam
6 ejector, while the motive steam is higher pressure steam extracted from the LPT. The motive steam
7 compresses the entrained vapor resulting in a middle-pressure steam that is used to drive a LT-MED process.
8 The remaining exhaust steam from the turbine is condensed through the condenser of the power cycle.

9 In Configuration #3 (see Fig. 3), a TVC-MED is integrated into the CSP plant using high pressure steam
10 from LPT to feed a steam ejector coupled to a MED plant. The total exhaust steam from the turbine is
11 condensed in the cooling system of the power cycle.

12 Finally, Configuration #4 (see Fig. 4) corresponds to the basic combination of a RO system with a CSP
13 plant, in which the desalination process is completely independent from the power generation.
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15 **3. Techno-economic analysis**

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17 The techno-economic analysis was carried out for two specific geographical locations chosen as
18 representative of different regions with widespread development of CSP plants and an increasing water
19 deficit planned to be mitigated with desalination: Almería, in Spain, and Abu Dhabi, in United Arab
20 Emirates. Almería has a high solar irradiation, with a Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI) value of around
21 1990 kWh/m²-year, similar to that of the north of Africa and other Mediterranean shores. Abu Dhabi has a
22 DNI of roughly 1925 kWh/m²-year [13], a value similar to other locations in the Arabian Gulf. The analysis
23 was carried out for three different cooling technologies typically available in commercial power plants: once-
24 through, evaporative water cooling and dry air cooling, except for Configuration #1 in which the LT-MED
25 unit replaces the condenser in the PT-CSP plant.
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27 *3.1. Thermodynamic analysis*

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29 The calculations of the Power and Desalination (P&D) cycle were performed as shown in Fig.5.

30 Firstly, the steam temperature at the outlet of the turbine was determined from meteorological data
31 considering a reference day as the design point and from the cooling system selected for the analysis. Then,
32 the procedure consisted of an iterative calculation of the sizes of the steam turbine and the desalination plant.
33 The former was calculated to meet the required net power generation at design conditions. The latter was
34 sized to satisfy the net fresh water production as determined by the computational simulation of
35 Configuration #1, where all the steam from the turbine must be condensed in the desalination unit and this
36 fixes the fresh water production according to the thermal efficiency of the distillation plant. The iteration was
37 required since the internal electricity consumption of the various plant components and the fresh water
38 consumed internally in the power plant are dependent on the CSP and desalination plant gross capacities,
39 which are still not known at the beginning of the calculation.

40 Both the power cycle and the desalination plant were modeled and then integrated to solve the P&D
41 cycle. The model of the power cycle was implemented within Engineering Equation Solver software
42 environment. All the components associated with the power cycle were analyzed by steady-flow energy and
43 mass transfer equations. The model of the MED plant in case of Configurations #1, #2 and #3, was developed
44 and validated by the authors with real data from a pilot MED plant located at the Plataforma Solar de
45 Almería [14]. It was implemented within MATLAB software environment and integrated into the power
46 plant model to run the simulations. In the case of MED with TVC, a semi-empirical model developed by El-
47 Dessouky [15] was additionally used for the calculation of the steam ejector mass flow rates.

48 The steam condensation temperature, T_{ST} , (i.e. the steam temperature at the outlet of the turbine) was
49 established according to the refrigeration method used and the ambient conditions of the location. The lower
50 this temperature, the higher the power plant efficiency is. For both locations, the 21st of September at solar
51 noon was selected as the design point in order to avoid a large difference between summer and winter plant
52 performance. The solar irradiance and meteorological values of interest at this point are shown in Table 1.

53 In the case of once-through cooling, the T_{ST} was determined from the seawater temperature adding a
54 temperature differential in the condenser. This temperature difference was set at 10 °C, as usually established
55 by environmental regulations. An average value of the seawater temperature was taken for both locations
56 based on published data from commercial desalination plants in the corresponding regions [16], namely:
57 35 °C for Abu Dhabi and 25 °C for Almería. In evaporative cooling, the T_{ST} was calculated as the sum of the
58 wet bulb temperature (determined from the ambient temperature and the relative humidity) and a temperature
59 difference consisting on the addition of three different factors: the tower approach (the difference between
60 the cooling tower outlet and the wet bulb temperature), the cooling tower range (the difference between the
61 cooling tower inlet and the cooling tower outlet) and the difference between the inlet and outlet temperature
62 in the condenser. The data were taken from Andasol-1 plant [17]: 7 °C, 8 °C and 3 °C respectively. Finally,
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5 in dry cooling, the T_{ST} was determined from the dry bulb temperature (ambient temperature) adding a
6 temperature differential in the aero-condenser, which was considered to be 22 °C based on the average values
7 from a report disseminated by the U.S. Department of Energy [18]. The resulting T_{ST} at point 10 in
8 Configurations #2, #3 and #4 are shown in Table 2.

9 Table 3 shows the rest of the operating conditions used for the simulation of P&D cycle, which were
10 taken from a typical commercial plant [17]. The calculation was firstly performed for Configuration #1,
11 which allowed defining the net fresh water production for the rest of configurations (point 13 in Figs. 1 to 4).
12 The number of effects of the MED plant was set according to the seawater temperature of the location of
13 interest, since it establishes the vapor temperature in the last effect and therefore the lift temperature in the
14 plant that determines the number of effects. For the location of Almería, a 14-effect MED plant was selected
15 whereas an 11-effect MED plant was considered in the case of Abu Dhabi.

16 In addition to the fresh water production, the GOR associated to this production was obtained from the
17 computational simulation of the first configuration. The GOR is defined as the mass of distillate, $M_{d,gross}$,
18 produced for every mass unit of external steam supplied to the desalination unit. In the case of the LT-MED
19 plant (Configurations #1 and #2), the latter is the steam entering into the first effect of the MED unit,
20 q_s (Point 11 in Figs. 1 and 2), and in the case of the TVC-MED (Configuration #3), the external steam is that
21 supplied as motive steam into the ejector, q_{mv} (part of steam extracted in Point 8, Fig. 3) [19]. Therefore, the
22 GOR in each case is defined as follows:

$$23 \quad GOR_{LT-MED} = \frac{M_{d,gross}}{q_s} \quad (1)$$

$$24 \quad GOR_{TVC-MED} = \frac{M_{d,gross}}{q_{mv}} \quad (2)$$

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29 Table 4 shows the values of the GOR obtained for the LT-MED plant (Configuration #1 and #2), and for
30 the TVC-MED plant (Configuration #3) according to the operation conditions shown in Table 3. The net
31 fresh water production resulting from the simulation of Configuration #1 is also shown in Table 4

32 As explained before, the same net fresh water production was used in all cases. Moreover, a slightly
33 larger gross fresh water production was considered accounting for internal consumption in the power plant
34 (cleaning of the solar collectors, water consumption within the power block, etc.). Also, in the case of
35 evaporative cooling, an additional amount of water must be produced to be used in the evaporative tower (see
36 Table 5).

37 The net power generation (50 MW_e) was considered to be the same in all configurations. This arises
38 from the gross power production after subtracting the internal power consumption by the pumps, and the
39 power consumption required by the desalination process and the cooling system.

40 For the calculation of the power required by the desalination plant, a specific electric consumption of
41 1.5 kWh/m³ of distillate production was assumed in the case of the MED plant for both locations [16]. For
42 the RO, a value of 3 kWh/m³ was chosen for Almería, and 4 kWh/m³ for Abu Dhabi due to the different
43 conditions of salinity and temperature of the raw seawater [16]. The above described power consumptions do
44 not take into account the pumping of feedwater from the sea to the desalination plants neither the cooling
45 seawater pumping for the condenser of the MED plant. They were calculated assuming that the desalination
46 plants are located close to the CSP plant at an altitude of 150 m above the sea level and a distance from the
47 sea of about 60 km. This assumption is based on the commercial CSP located closest to the sea (Shams 1 in
48 Abu Dhabi), and in order to avoid the problems of lower DNI and the conditions of saline environment that
49 could damage the parabolic-trough mirrors.

50 For the power consumption of the different cooling systems selected, a series of considerations were
51 taken into account:

- 52 • In the case of dry cooling, it was required a 5 % increase in the electricity produced annually [20].
- 53 • For once-through cooling, the electricity consumed by the pump that circulates the water from the
54 sea through the condenser was determined considering the same values of altitude and distance
55 from the sea mentioned before. Moreover, a specific seawater flow rate of 87.08 m³/MW_eh was
56 taken into account as required to condense the exhaust steam from the turbine [18].
- 57 • In the case of evaporative water cooling, a specific electricity consumption of 0.0329 MW_e/MW
58 was considered [21].

59 Once the P&D cycle was solved, the solar field size was determined considering the net output thermal
60 capacity required by the cycle. The model of the solar field was implemented in MATLAB taking into
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account the collector's thermal losses, its efficiency curve and the corresponding energy and mass balances [9]. In order to analyze the annual solar contribution for the selected design point, the annual solar fraction, which is defined as the percentage of the thermal power requirement that is provided by the solar field, was calculated. For this purpose, an annual simulation program was developed and implemented in MATLAB for a typical meteorological year of each location.

The simulations of the P&D cycle allowed obtaining the value of thermodynamic parameters such as the thermal power required and the overall efficiency together with the solar field size required.

3.2. Economic analysis

The economic analysis was addressed determining the electricity and water costs of the proposed configurations. The following definition of Levelized Electricity Cost (*LEC*) was used [22]:

$$LEC = \frac{crf \times K_{invest} + K_{O\&M} + K_{fuel}}{E_{net}} \quad (3)$$

where K_{invest} is the total investment of the plant, $K_{O\&M}$ are the annual operation and maintenance costs, K_{fuel} is the annual fuel cost (which is only applicable in the case of solar energy with backup), E_{net} is the annual net electricity delivered to the grid and crf is the capital recovery factor, which is calculated from:

$$crf = \frac{k_d(1 + k_d)^n}{(1 + k_d)^n - 1} + K_{insurance} \quad (4)$$

being k_d (6.5 %) the real debt interest rate, n is the depreciation period in years (20 years) and $K_{insurance}$ is the annual insurance rate (1 %).

A similar procedure was used for the Levelized Water Cost (*LWC*) estimation. Table 6 shows the values used for the economic parameters, which were based on published data by NREL [23] and personal communication from CSP experts [24].

4. Results and discussion

The results of the simulations are shown in Tables 7 and 8, which list the most relevant parameters of the P&D cycle and the solar field in each configuration. The parameters that indicate how good a configuration is from a thermodynamic point of view are mainly the thermal power required by the P&D cycle (given by P_{th}) and the global efficiency of the P&D cycle (η_{th}). The size of the solar field (A_a) is a function of the thermal power required by the cycle, and the solar fraction (F_s) the annual solar contribution for this solar field design. Also shown in case of Configurations #2 and #3 are the steam flow rates needed in the ejector q_{mv} and q_{ent} , which give an idea of the penalty in the power production due to the use of steam from the LPT. Regarding the cooling system, the tables show the fresh water flow rate consumed in the evaporative tower (F_{fw}) and the seawater flow rate circulating through the once-through cooling system of the power plant (F_{sw}). Also indicated are the gross power (P_{gross}) and fresh water production ($M_{d,gross}$). Finally, the results of the economic analysis are given by the levelized electric cost (*LEC*) and the levelized water cost (*LWC*).

The results obtained for Abu Dhabi (Table 7) show that the integration of a LT-MED into a CSP plant was the most efficient option thermodynamically. The reduction in the power cycle efficiency resulting from preventing the expansion of the exhaust steam to a lower pressure (Configuration #1) was smaller than that due to using high pressure steam from the turbine to feed the steam ejector (Configurations #2 and #3). A more interesting result is the fact that the coupling with a LT-MED through thermocompression (Configuration #2) was also more efficient thermodynamically and in terms of electricity costs than the combination with RO (Configuration #4) in the case of using dry cooling in the power cycle (28.41 % in the overall efficiency of Configuration #2 against 27.58 % of Configuration #4; 17.96 c€/kWh in the *LEC* of Configuration #2 against 18.97 c€/kWh of Configuration #4), which is the usual condensation process selected in the Arabian Gulf [13].

With respect to the economic results, Configuration #1 was also more favourable for all cases in terms of electricity costs (*LEC*) due mainly to the extra power that the CSP must generate for the cooling system in the rest of configurations. As seen in Table 7, a gross power of 63.59 MW_e must be produced in the case of Configuration #4 with dry cooling against 55.36 MW_e that should be produced in Configuration #1. This meant an increase of about 14 % in the *LEC*. In the case of water costs (*LWC*), Configuration #4 was the most optimal due to the lower investment costs of RO, except in the case of evaporative cooling. Using this

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5 refrigeration method, an additional fresh water flow rate of 4462 m³/day was needed in the evaporative
6 tower, which required a desalination plant 11 % larger. The difference of the *LWC* in favour of Configuration
7 #4 with respect to Configurations #1 and #2 was not that high, though (less than 5 %) and might not be a
8 reason strong enough for choosing it, especially considering the further problems that RO desalination can
9 have in the Arabian Gulf, such as red algae blooms and problems derived from the high seawater salinity.
10 Therefore, the integration of a LT-MED in the CSP plant can be preferable in the Arabian Gulf. However, the
11 good results from Configuration #2 with dry cooling make it a good solution regarding the CSP industry
12 reluctance to fully eliminate the condenser of the power cycle (Configuration #1). A further advantage of this
13 configuration is that it offers the possibility of a better adaptation to the yearly electricity and water demand
14 curves: since the desalination plant is the same as in Configuration #1, the LT-MED could be connected in a
15 way which allows switching between the thermocompression mode (Configuration #2) and the direct use of
16 the exhaust steam (Configuration #1), .

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18 In the case of Almería (Table 8) the ambient conditions allow the exhaust steam from the turbine to
19 expand to lower pressures. This improvement in the power generation efficiency compensates the extra
20 power consumed by the condenser and the higher electricity consumption by the RO in Configuration #4
21 with respect to the LT-MED. The evaporative cooling implies even lower exhaust steam pressures and lower
22 electric consumption in the condenser, which makes Configuration #4 with this refrigeration method better
23 thermodynamically than Configuration #1 (the overall efficiency of the latter was 30.02 % against 30.85 % of
24 the former). The difference with respect to electricity costs was negligible in this case (0.3 %) and the *LWC*
25 were slightly better for the case of LT-MED (the RO plant was 9 % larger to supply the additional fresh
26 water needed in the evaporative tower). For the rest of cases, Configuration #1 was more optimal
27 thermodynamically than Configuration #4 due to the full replacement of the condenser that eliminated the
28 additional power consumed by the cooling system. The extra power that should be produced in Configuration
29 #4 for once-through and dry cooling increased the *LEC* by 10 %. However, the *LWC* were a bit lower (4 %
30 lower) for Configuration #4 with these refrigeration methods compared with Configuration #1.

31 At these lower steam outlet pressures, Configurations #2 and #3 were also more strongly penalized with
32 respect to Configuration #4. Unlike in Abu Dhabi, there was no case in which Configuration #2 was better
33 than #4. In the case of dry cooling, Configuration #4 had a global efficiency 4 % higher than
34 Configuration #2. The costs were very similar, being the difference in the *LEC* negligible (less than 1 %) and
35 the *LWC* of Configuration #4 4 % lower than for Configuration #2.

36 Since the only case that can be more favourable thermodynamic and economically with respect to
37 Configuration #4 implies the full replacement of the condenser (Configuration #1), it seems more realistic for
38 the Mediterranean basin to opt for the combination of CSP with RO. However, in the cases that cooling
39 systems are other than the evaporative cooling, the differences are not so large and Configuration #2 could be
40 contemplated as an option. Improvements in the investment cost or the efficiency of the LT-MED could help
41 counterbalance this scenario.

42 **4. Conclusions**

43 A techno-economic analysis for different options of the combination of large-scale solar desalination by
44 with CSP was carried out in two representative locations of the Mediterranean Sea and the Arabian Gulf.
45 Several CSP+MED configurations besides the direct coupling with CSP (CSP+LT-MED) were considered
46 and compared with the combination of RO with CSP, and the three conventional refrigeration processes were
47 taken into account for the power cycle.

48 Taking into account the results of the analysis and the operational constrains of the CSP plants, the
49 recommended combination for CSP and desalination in the Arabian Gulf is the integration in the power cycle
50 of a LT-MED through thermocompression (LT-MED+TVC). The integration of a LT-MED replacing the
51 condenser of the power cycle was the most efficient configuration, but the integration through
52 thermocompression offers the further advantage of decoupling the water and power production, which means
53 an increase of reliability and better adaptation to the yearly electricity and water demand curves.

54 On the other hand, in the Mediterranean basin the direct use of electricity generated by a CSP plant in a
55 RO unit is more difficult to surpass. Only when the condenser is fully replaced by the desalination plant, the
56 integration of a LT-MED in the power cycle gives better results, but not in the case of using evaporative
57 cooling, which is the most usual case for CSP plants in the Mediterranean area. However, although the
58 integration of a LT-MED with thermocompression was not so favorable in the Mediterranean case, the
59 differences with respect to the combination of CSP with RO were not too large, and in some cases negligible.
60 When dry cooling is preferred as the cooling system in the power cycle to minimize water consumption, the
61 integration of a LT-MED with thermocompression into a CSP plant offers an opportunity for the
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5 implementation of solar desalination in the Mediterranean shores.
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7 *Nomenclature*

8 P_{th} net output thermal capacity (MW_{th})
9 q_{mv} motive steam flow rate (kg/s)
10 q_{ent} entrained vapor flow rate (kg/s)
11 η_{th} global efficiency
12 F_{fw} fresh water flow rate (m³/day)
13 F_{sw} seawater flow rate (m³/day)
14 *GOR* Gain Output Ratio
15 $M_{d,net}$ net fresh water production (m³/day)
16 $M_{d,gross}$ gross fresh water production (m³/day)
17 P_{gross} gross power production (MW_e)
18 A_a aperture area (m²)
19 F_s solar fraction
20 q_s heating steam flow rate (kg/s)
21 *LEC* Levelized electricity cost (c€/kWh)
22 *LWC* Levelized water cost (€/m³)
23 *crf* capital recovery factor
24 K_{invest} total investment of the plant (€)
25 $K_{O\&M}$ annual operation and maintenance costs (€)
26 K_{fuel} annual fuel cost (€)
27 E_{net} net electricity delivered to the grid (GWh)
28 k_d real debt interest rate (%)
29 n depreciation period (years)
30 $K_{insurance}$ annual insurance rate (%)

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27 **Figure captions**

- 28 **Fig. 1.** Flow diagram of Configuration #1
29 **Fig. 2.** Flow diagram of Configuration #2
30 **Fig. 3.** Flow diagram of Configuration #3
31 **Fig. 4.** Flow diagram of Configuration #4
32 **Fig. 5.** Flow diagram for calculation procedure
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Table 1: Ambient conditions at 21st September solar noon for Abu Dhabi and Almería

Location	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Direct normal irradiance (W/m ²)	Relative Humidity (%)
Abu Dhabi	37.1	853	47
Almería	27.1	884	43

Table 2: Turbine Outlet Steam Temperatures for each refrigeration method used in the power cycle

	Once Through		Evaporative Water Cooling		Dry Cooling	
	Abu Dhabi	Almería	Abu Dhabi	Almería	Abu Dhabi	Almería
T_{ST} (°C)	45	35	45	37	60	50

Table 3. Operation conditions set for the thermodynamic simulation of the systems shown in Figs. 1-4

Point in the diagram	Parameters	Values
1	Temperature and Pressure	373 °C, 100 bar
2	Pressure	33.5 bar
3	Pressure	18.5 bar
4	Temperature and Pressure	373.4 °C, 16.5 bar
5	Pressure	14 bar
6	Pressure	6.18 bar
7	Pressure	3.04 bar
8	Pressure	1.17 bar *
9	Pressure	0.37 bar
11	Pressure	0.3121 bar
12	Pressure	0.1817 bar **
14	Pressure	8.38 bar
15	Pressure	103 bar

*Vapor from the fourth extraction of LPT is used to avoid high penalty in the overall efficiency of the power cycle [10]

**The entrained vapor is taken for an intermediate effect of the MED plant.

Table 4: *GOR* and net fresh water production in both locations

Location	<i>GOR</i>		Net fresh water production (m ³ /day)
	LT-MED	TVC-MED	
Abu Dhabi	8.4	10	35607
Almería	10	12	42927

Table 5: Specific fresh water consumptions for the internal water consumed in the P&D cycle

	Evaporative Water Cooling	Mirror cleaning	Power block	Other internal consumptions
Specific fresh water consumption (m ³ /MW _e h)	3	0.07	0.175	0.0029

Table 6. Economic values for the calculation of *LEC* and *LWC*

	Values
Hours thermal energy storage	6.5 hours
Plant availability (power and desalination plants)	96%
Land preparation and infrastructure	15 \$/m ²
Solar collector	150 \$/m ²
Heat transfer fluid and hydraulic circuit	90 \$/m ²
Thermal storage system	35 \$/KW _{th} h
Power block	1,000,000 \$/kW _{gross}
Auxiliary gas burner	60 \$/KW _{th}
Reverse Osmosis plant	1207 \$/(m ³ /day)*
Multi-effect Distillation plant	1230 \$/(m ³ /day)*

*[25]

Table 7. Results obtained from the techno-economic analysis in Abu Dhabi

	Units	Conf #1	Conf #2 (dry)	Conf #2 (evap)	Conf #2 (once)	Conf #3 (dry)	Conf #3 (evap)	Conf #3 (once)	Conf #4 (dry)	Conf #4 (evap)	Conf #4 (once)
η_{th}	[-]	30.41	28.41	28.05	26.42	26.13	26.33	24.46	27.58	29.65	26.86
P_{th}	MW _{th}	164	176	178	189	191	190	204	181	169	186
F_{fw}	m ³ /day	n/a	n/a	341	n/a	n/a	4043	n/a	n/a	4462	n/a
F_{sw}	m ³ /day	n/a	n/a	n/a	33524	n/a	n/a	133524	n/a	n/a	145228
q_{ent}	kg/s	n/a	21.72	13.38	13.26	29.68	33.01	29.71	n/a	n/a	n/a
q_{mv}	kg/s	n/a	27.44	36.25	35.93	41.32	45.95	41.36	n/a	n/a	n/a
$M_{d,gross}$	m ³ /day	35950	35959	36301	35985	35979	40016	36012	35997	40448	36025
P_{gross}	MW _e	55.36	55.76	55.65	59.89	58.03	57.05	63.89	63.59	62.95	69.49
A_a	m ²	807690	866550	876360	931950	941760	935220	1007160	892710	830580	915600
F_s	[-]	53.96	54.11	54.02	54.09	54.07	54.10	54.13	54.09	54.11	54.13
LEC	c€/kWh	16.58	17.96	17.73	18.95	19.46	18.76	20.38	18.97	17.40	19.22
LWC	€/m ³	0.83	0.83	0.92	0.83	0.83	0.91	0.83	0.79	0.88	0.79

Table 8. Results obtained from the techno-economic analysis in Almería

	Units	Conf #1	Conf #2 (dry)	Conf #2 (evap)	Conf #2 (once)	Conf #3 (dry)	Conf #3 (evap)	Conf #3 (once)	Conf #4 (dry)	Conf #4 (evap)	Conf #4 (once)
η_{th}	[-]	30.02	27.86	27.32	25.49	26.14	26.27	24.48	28.92	30.85	27.95
P_{th}	MW _{th}	167	179	183	196	191	190	204	173	162	179
F_{fw}	m ³ /day	n/a	n/a	444	n/a	n/a	4084	n/a	n/a	4424	n/a
F_{sw}	m ³ /day	n/a	n/a	n/a	48054	n/a	n/a	134798	n/a	n/a	145109
q_{ent}	kg/s	n/a	16.16	9.65	8.70	29.82	32.63	29.85	n/a	n/a	n/a
q_{mv}	kg/s	n/a	33.64	40.67	41.13	41.51	45.43	41.55	n/a	n/a	n/a
$M_{d,gross}$	m ³ /day	43274	43285	43730	43317	43301	47380	43335	43310	47723	43340
P_{gross}	MW _e	56.08	56.50	56.44	61.49	58.62	57.62	64.50	63.24	62.42	69.43
A_a	m ²	752100	810960	827310	886170	863280	860010	922140	781530	732480	807690
F_s	[-]	47.52	47.56	47.59	47.55	46.32	47.55	47.52	47.59	47.58	47.52
LEC	c€/kWh	18.73	20.35	20.24	21.79	21.69	20.95	22.69	20.37	18.79	20.78
LWC	€/m ³	0.96	0.96	1.05	0.96	0.96	1.05	0.96	0.92	1.01	0.92

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